

BRIEF RESEARCH OF THE NATURAL CRISIS-MANAGEMENT APPROACH IN THE INTERNATIONAL TECH-COMPANIES

Author(s)*: Adina-Alexandra BRETAN
Position: PhD Student
University: Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Address: Cluj-Napoca, Memorandumului St., No. 28, Romania
E-mail: aadinaabretan@gmail.com
Webpage: <http://www.utcluj.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – Gain a theoretical overview of the crisis types and of the operational crisis management during a natural crisis, which is built around the current global pandemic situation with the focus on the digital business sector, namely on the tech-companies.

Methodology/approach - A literature review related to the crisis management, a peer review based on online-structured interviews and a conceptual framework create the epicenter of this paper work.

Findings – The international tech-companies are powerful organizations that are stable due to their global influence. They are the ones that play an important role in the recovery of the economy, both on national and global level.

Research limitations/implications – The research has been performed on more levels, beginning with theoretical literature references and continuing with studying current articles from official sources in accordance with the paper's subject. The practical part of the research has been conducted on an employee level, rather than on a managerial level.

Practical implications – A qualitative research was performed for the practical analysis of the current crisis, considering the personal experiences of ten individuals who currently professionally act in in two different IT-companies. The interviews were carried over during the pandemic, exclusively in online environments.

Originality/value – The most recent articles from the web, written during the current global pandemic, by both international journals and even tech-companies, have been thoroughly analysed and after considering every aspect in accordance with the paper's subject they have been presented within this article, being supplemented with a practical involvement.

Key words: Crisis Management, International Tech-Companies, Covid-19 Crisis

Introduction

Over the years, the world was pushed to face, fight and overcome various crisis. One can relate of such a situation according to (Rodrigues, Quarantelli, & Dynes, 2006) when a community of people remarks a sudden and urgent threat to their core, life-sustaining values, dealing with it under uncertainty. It is considered a critical point in the road of development, implying both threat and opportunity. As (Evans & et.al., 2005) and (Spence & et.al., 2007) describe that there are numerous types of crisis, such as: natural (public health threat), financial, strategic, chemical, technological, man-made. Particularly considering an international organization, (Boin, 2008) lists some possible causes that may lead to a crisis: bribery, security breach, natural disasters that disrupt a major product/service or recall key stakeholders, technological breakdown.

The natural crisis disrupt major services, destroy organizational information base and headquarters, eliminate clients and employees (Boin, 2008) and are defined as large-scale events framed by potential loss of life or property (SAMSHA, 2020). The problems of the international companies at an operational level consist in: mobility restrictions, difficult supply of essentials, import-export restrictions, depreciation of the financial performance and ruin of the reputation, redefined relationship with customers, employees, stakeholders (OECD, 2020). There are multiple reactions that are being established in such

constelations: as per (Bundy & et.al., 2016) “total responsibility approach, focused on reacquainting the importance of an organization’s responsibilities towards stakeholders, creating a response strategy, while other companies reflect their reactions by stabilizing revenues, aligning their businesses, building new digital competences, such as: data-driven, agile, cloud, automation, e-commerce and security”.

Research Methodology

This paper discusses the current situation of the crisis management among the tech-companies floating during the global COVID-19 pandemic crisis. The aim is to identify how are the operational processes within this industry, both managerial and support, affected.

A literature review, a conceptual framework and a peer feedback have been performed.

- The first step was to identify the information sources, such as literature, web (up to date articles, journals, websites), personal observations based on experience and peer feedback. The start point has been to choose 30 literature sources from which 20 were filtered according to the common points with this paper’s theme, remaining 16 such references to carry out during the process. Nevertheless, 15 web sources have been identified and analysed, wherefrom only eight have molded to the subject approached. The ideas were gathered and united into achieving a theoretical overview of the crisis management in the actual context of the global pandemic.
- Afterwards, a qualitative research method has been used, considering the personal experiences of ten individuals that professionally act in two IT-companies. The interviews were held during the Coronavirus-pandemic, in an offline environment, via Skype and phone. During the aftermath the gathered information has been thoroughly analysed and furthermore discussed and also interpreted. The goal was to appraise the reactions of the tech-companies and acquire lessons and innovative solutions.

Following the empirical research and the literature review, a conceptual framework was built, concluding by stating that the international tech-companies are powerful organizations that play a crucial role in the national and international economy. In the end, they are considered important actors in the recovery process, being the engine of many industries. The crisis management of operations plays an important part in this framework, being carefully taken care of by the CEOs and the strategic management teams of the businesses. Nevertheless great solutions have been discovered due to the unusual crisis of the Coronavirus, realizing that the virtual and digital environments can provide many advantages nowadays, other than the traditional human-made elaborations.

Background

Within this brief research of literature review, there are some subjects that have been analyzed, such as the characteristics of the IT-companies, the crisis and the crisis management of operations.

Particularities of Tech-Companies

The IT-companies act among the businesses in different ways in comparison with other types of organizations. The following tables presents their fundamentals, highlights the types of tech-companies based on the market segment they are involved in, compresses some characteristics that differentiate them from other business typologies and creates an overview of the service-shared delivery.

This type of organizations usually act on an international level, aiming to achieve a global status. They are specialized on IT-services, meaning that various actors work according to the client’s requirements, using a common language and common tools, with the purpose of delivering the tasks required by the client in a qualitative way and within the agreed timeline.

Table 1 Particularities of Tech-Companies
(based on literature review and web sources listed in column 1)

Source	Fundamentals
(Bailetti, 2012)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Tech-companies focus on investment in projects, assembling and deploying specialists and heterogeneous assets -Purpose: flourishing the scientific and technological knowledge, in order to create and capture value for the company -Explore and exploit technological knowledge for a period of time
(Blomerley, 2017) (Wu, Garg, & Buyya, 2011)	<p>Types of tech-companies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tech-hardware: digitalization, gadgets - Software-as-a-service: delivery of services based upon service level agreements - Extension of offline business: due to convenience - A marketplace: networks and platforms that connect buyers and sellers
(Dovleac & Balasescu, 2013) (Hout, Porter, & Rudden, 2020)	<p>Characteristics of international tech-companies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uncertainty of problem solving possibilities - Resources: chosen and provided by highly qualified individuals - Orientation: targeting the technological arrays - Well-structured and qualitative infrastructure - Service networks - Maintenance, installation, high-tech functionality services - Continuous development of the technology - Innovation strategies for competitive advantages within unpredictable markets - New business models - Major investment projects - Delivery of services in high and low labor-cost countries - A country-by-country market position, included in a worldwide portfolio - Financial investments, marketing investments, investment in the distribution network - A unique global strategy
(Wei, 2011)	<p>Service-orientated tech-companies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Autonomous, reusable, unique and portable products - Services: based on arithmetic calculations, programs, maintenance activities, all in virtual, distributed environments - Cloud computing as a solution for cost saving - High Service Availability - Different service providers - Markup language techniques: common communication, implementation and understanding - Service Level Agreements (SLAs) - Service analysis - Reputation of the services - Software-service: separate business models - Service-based information, assurance and privacy

Crisis and their impact on the operational management

The term of crisis is a general definition of an unusual situation, but it can have various root-causes that need different approaches and solutions. Among this concept, over the years, there have been developed some crisis-models. Their aim is to frame the event within a standard and afterwards to build an actual scenario of the situation and of the possible solutions. The management of such disasters is very important, so it takes places granularly, on organizational managerial levels, such as operational, strategic and support management.

Table 2 Crisis and their impact on the operational management within a tech-company
(based on a literature review and web-sources, cited in the first column)

Authorship	Outcome
(Boin, 2008)	Crisis: a critical point, a milestone, in a series of events that can be considered as threatening for a community of people due to uncertainty, under pressure of time.
(Evans & et.al., 2005) (Nojoumi & et.al., 2015) (Gundel, 2005)	Crisis typologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Natural: sudden and unpredictable threat, various negative effects, hard to foresee. Usually not due to human mistakes. -Financial: cash flow problems, requires immediate actions, can be foreseen -Strategic: changes in the business environment, can be prevented by avoiding risky decisions -Smoldering (man-made): disruption that causes injuries to lives and properties, corporate wrong-doing -Technological: breakdown or failure of technological systems. Can be prevented
(Evans & et.al., 2005) (Ahmad & Mat, 2013) (Booth, 1993)	Models of the crisis management: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The "Cobra"-model, by Seymour and Moore: sudden, comes as a shock and feels as a threat. Reaction: an immediate response based on the known and trusted -The 4Rs, four independent phases of a crisis, defined by Roberts (1994): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pre-Event 2. Emergency 3. Intermediate 4. Long-Term --The "Python"-model, by Seymour and Moore: gradually, increasing threat. Reaction: once the crisis is being recognized. In this context a double-loop-learning has been highlighted: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emergent Knowing - Paradigm Shift - New understanding -Slatter's crisis susceptibility model: economic side. The effectiveness of the decisions according to managerial and organizational characteristics and frames -Booth and the process model: identification of common features of various crisis. Approach: from general to simple -The crisis lifecycle, by Seymour and Moore: activities and decisions that are being taken during a crisis, from planning to implementation - Clarke and Varma: risk management as a strategic process
(Christiaens, Moreau, & Richez, 2020) (2020, 2020) (Cluj24.ro, 2020)	Operational crisis management: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Review of the IT-organization, procedures, tools and project portfolio to ensure adaptation to new business paradigms. -Re-definition of the IT-Target Operating Model, in terms of IT service and capabilities (related KPIs, competences, resources, procedures, tools). -The investment projects are frozen, due to uncertainty and due to the risk of failure along the process -Liquidity resources: protected by stopping the uncritical interventions -Focus: possible risks and action plans for urgency situations. -Aim: analyze and identify the moment when the client represents a risk for the company -New recovery scenarios concerning the relationship between the companies and their active and possible clients -Continuity plan of the operations: infrastructure, raw materials, materials for a considerable timeframe -Work from home initiative
(ManagementEvents, 2020) (WHO, 2020)	Levels of impact of the pandemic crisis: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Short term: on the revenues- predictable fall of 10-15% -Long term: business continuity planning (BCP) and scenario planning -Post-crisis: return to normal -Local level: businesses are being first of all individually affected -National level: the multinational companies are directly dependent on the country's economy standard -Global level: the international businesses that act on a global level suffer as a whole

The variety of crisis is the result of a complex and dynamic world. They are either man-made or human independent. The management of the international companies needs to create an emergency plan in case of a crisis, to foresee it at the right moment, and to make the right decisions at the right time. Such events affect the organizations on more levels, according to the root-cause and severity.

Epirical Research

The empirical research of the paper presents a process-map and the affected areas by the current pandemic crisis, created by the author, based on personal experiences within an international, global, tech-company. Afterwards, as per ten structured interviews, a peer review is next, aiming to analyze the facts and the solutions during the Covid-19-crisis, from the perspectives of other employees.

Engineering of the Business Processes in a Service-Orientated IT-Company

The following figure reflects the process-map of an international tech-companies, with an unique global strategies, created by the author due to personal experiences and analysis.

Figure 1 Process Map in an international tech-company
(personal elaboration based on facts and experience)

The figure from above orchestrates a process-map within an international company, orientated to service-shared activities. First of all, it highlights the strategic processes of the business:

- CEO & Deputy CEO: establish strategies on a global level, sustain the maturity of the company and try to expand
- Technology Top Managers: coordinate the project related activities and make decisions, each on divergent technologies
- Quality Managers: maintain the quality standards, redefine the actual status
- Sales: gain new projects and new clients within the market
- Environment Managers and Commercial: place the business within a market and keeps up with the competition
- Sustainability Managers: Long-term achievements
- Risk Managers: calculate the risk possibilities and statistically prevent different types of crises
- Security Managers: data privacy, workers security

The support processes are meant to help the main activities of the business work in normal parameters, such as:

- Finance: budget allocation, remuneration
- HR and WFM: human resources recruitment and employee care
- Accounting: incomes and taxes
- Marketing: marketing strategy, advertising, events
- IT-Support: secure the soft-and hardware functionality and the network infrastructure

The operational processes imply:

- Process-Flow Know-How: understanding the internal process procedures of the client
- Software-Architecture understanding: comprehending the interconnected information objects of the software
- Software-Maintenance: monitor and manage software reactions and responses
- Infrastructure-Maintenance: ensure the netting of the physical and virtual components
- Research & Development: continuous improvement and innovation
- Implementations: accomplish new requirements, introduce them in the client's product and adapt them to the current constallation and standards
- Testing: try-outs of the changes and new implementations

Operational Processes Affected by the Crisis Nowadays

The next table illustrates the level of impact caused by the current Covid-19-crisis among some operational processes of the international tech-companies, with globalized services.

Table 3 Affected operational processes in international tech-businesses due to the pandemic crisis (personal elaboration based on facts and experience)

Operational Process	Level of shock	Impact	Description
Process-Flow Know-How	Neutral	No visible changes	The process-flow remained unchanged during the lockdown
Software Architecture Understanding	Increase	Visible changes	During the lockdown the time has been used to perform changes in advance, so the software architectures changed and therefore also their level of understanding increased
Software Maintenance	Decrease	Visible dchanges	The no-production situation lead to less problems than usual. Less technical issues than normally
Infrastructure Maintenance	Neutral	Balance-increase of the changes and decrease of the load	In a normal work environment the load of infastructure maintenance activities is high, but during a lockdown is none, so the agreed transformations involve more maintenance activities.
Research and Development	Increase	No visible changes, but lots of experiments	New solutions, ideas of innovation
Implementations	Virtual-Increase	Visible changes	Due to increased research, the new solutions had to be implemented
	On site-Decrease	No visible changes	During the lockdown there were no on side implementations
Testing	Virtual-Increase	Visible changes	Due to increased research, the new solutions had to be tested, once developed, before the final implementation
	On side-Decrease	No visible changes	During the lockdown there were no on side tests necessary

The current pandemic managed to create mixed reactions and feelings among the CEOs of the international companies. A crucial moment for the world has been the lockdown, which stopped the production of various products and services. The reactions and the effects have been, however,

different, in each industry. The tech-companies have distinguished themselves through stability and strength. In some areas both negative and positive effects can be remarked, while in others everything remained unchanged.

Peer-Feedback

For the study, a qualitative research method was used around the perspective that every crisis is unique in its own way, causing particular effects to individuals and industries. The information was acquired out of structured interviews performed by one interviewer, the author, containing seven questions. The target group has implied employees of two international tech-companies that perform their job activities around operational processes. The interviews were carried out via Skype; afterwards the gathered information was analyzed based on the crisis management approach in times of global pandemic, according to the relevant literature background.

Table 4 Summary of the information gathered as a result of the interviews
(personal elaboration based on peer feedback and experience)

Goal	Opinions
1. Level of impact on the jobs	-High, because the communication possibilities and the social skills have been reduced, which lead to a higher settlement time -High, because of financial shortage (less or no bonuses, no events) -Low, because the cost cutting did not affect the employees directly
2. Ways in which the impacts have been highlighted within the company	-Restructured Organigram -Cost cutting -Work from home procedures -Allocated budget for health protection -Projects loss -Difficulty in gaining new clients
3. Ways in which the impacts have been highlighted in the clients activity	-Due to the lockdown the clients have closed their subsidiaries -Focus on development, implementations, digital changes and infrastructure -Pressure on achieving the targeted goals in advance in order to minimize the risks
4. Effects on the career	-Less promotion possibilities -Job changing due to higher pressure and requirements -Project loss, transition activities
5. Company's solutions	-Upgraded infrastructure -Online events for psychological support of the employees -Allocated budget for health care and disinfection -Resource management -Cost cutting -Less working days
6. Client's solutions	-Temporary close of the subsidiaries -Focus on the ongoing project that could be developed in a virtual environment -New providers (good financial offers, stable and strong providers) -Granular division of tasks -Special work shifts in order to keep the business ongoing
7. A different approach	-Financial support for the needy employees -Cost cutting instead of unemployment -Strategies for safe office work -Load should be shared

Aftermath of the peer-feedback:

- Risks (job loss, salary renegotiation, health) in service-shared, international tech-companies, are very low
- Specialized risk management (quick and correct measures, unexpected solutions)
- Employees perceive the taken measures differently
- Clients managed their requirements differently, based on their needs
- Different companies implemented different solutions

- The employees are generally satisfied with the measures
- There are various opinions on improvement potential and possibilities

The following figure represents a graphic representation of the peer-feedback results. The purpose is to visualize the effects of the pandemic crisis from the point of view of some employees in such companies, in order to highlight the reactions, perceptions and the quality of the operational management:

Figure 2 Peer Feedback Results (personal elaboration based on peer feedback and experience)

According to the graphic representation in figure 2 the conclusions sustain the idea that the international tech-companies that develop their business activities in a service-shared way, did not suffer exponentially during the pandemic crisis. They did, however, perform unexpected actions in this regard. The way the employees perceived the changes is different from company to company. The reason is that each organization calculated its own risks and planed its own emergency plan, based on the requirments of the active clients and on the continuity plans of wining new customers. Many interviewd employees are happy with the measures taken by their employer and wouldn't have changed anything, while others consider that some measures were too drastic.

Originality and Value

Covid-19 is the most recent crisis that needs to be correctly and urgently managed by the international companies worldwide. The pandemic lead to a global crisis with great negative and positive effects in the international businesses. While many business sectors have been on hold due to the lockdown and other governmental restrictions, the tech-companies have been scrambling since the beginning to support the local and global economy.

There are many discussions and scientific publications around the crisis management, for various crisis typologies, but few concerning the natural crisis within health disasters. Among the world pandemics, we encounter the Covid-19, since 2019 that appeared in a digital and modern world, while the last worldwide-declared pandemic was announced two centuries ago, when the globe lived in very different circumstances and the business concepts have been very different in comparison with their understanding and breakthrough.

The paper remarks itself because the analysis of the literature review is based on the most recent articles appeared on the web regarding the natural crisis management due to the coronavirus. Through the fact that the paper is being written during the global crisis, aiming to determine the most accurate and most recent information regarding this topic. Because the topic is being approached in the frames of

interviews among various persons that activate in the tech business sector, individuals that are being directly affected, at the time of the interviews and at the time of the crisis, created an accurate framework.

The paper brings a plus because the subject approached is currently being very deliberated and analyzed at the time being, serving for a better comprehension of the circumstances and trying to offer another perception of the current struggle of the international tech companies and their employees.

Conclusions

Natural crisis have great impacts of the industries. The health of the individuals is the most sensitive topic worldwide, which, in times of critical events, is placed on the top of any business's priority list. The Coronavirus-pandemic caused both negative and positive effects, for those international organizations that managed to see the opportunities. The tech-companies, that target the service delivery rather than own products manufacturing, perform their activities among various markets and aim scientific and technological innovations.

During the pandemic the world went through various crisis scenarios, which lead to emergency actions, decisions and measures. Most of the international IT-companies protected their revenue, liquidities and assets, their specialists and their clients. All the safety measures taken in this context went gradually from non to the current status. The employees are satisfied with the way their companies dealt with the crisis and recognize their efforts, not having to many different ideas to approach the situation.

The global tech-companies are probably the most stable businesses, as they perform their activities in various parts of the world, having both global and national strategies. They managed to use the times of the lockdown to go on with the innovations, implementations and scientific research, many of them creating new technologies in order to help among the current crisis context.

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